

Organisational Review for 2i2c

Prepared by:
Davina Sirisena
Founder

Tel: +44 7799 473070
Email: davina@makeadifference.digital

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	1
1. Executive Summary.....	2
Key Findings.....	2
Key Recommendations.....	2
2. Introduction.....	4
2.1. Purpose.....	4
2.2. Background.....	4
2.3. Method.....	5
3. Current State.....	7
3.1. Structure.....	7
3.2. Process.....	7
3.3. Culture & People.....	8
4. Analysis.....	10
4.1. No single owner of, or deep experience in, Product.....	10
4.2. The Engineering Manager’s focus and effectiveness are diluted by detailed day-to-day work management.....	12
4.3. Engineers feel overloaded and find it difficult to know what to prioritise.....	14
4.4. There is no-one with the bandwidth or responsibility to manage and facilitate cross-team work and processes.....	16
4.5. The process for decision making is unclear.....	18
4.6. There are inherent challenges with asynchronous working.....	19
4.7. There is widespread concern about stress and burnout.....	21
4.8. There is no-one with solid experience of people management or processes....	23
5. Conclusion.....	26
Appendix 1: Summary of Findings.....	27

1. Executive Summary

This report presents a comprehensive evaluation of your organisation's current state and provides strategic recommendations for sustainable growth.

You've initiated this assessment because you're facing challenges in knowing how to best scale your capacity to meet the growing demand. Your aim is to ensure that your organisation's structure, processes, and culture are well-aligned for future growth.

Our assessment, conducted through interviews, observations, and expert consultations, has identified key areas that require immediate attention.

Key Findings

Given 2i2c's relatively young age, several essential roles and functions have not yet been established. Consequently, there's a shortage of expertise and capacity needed for the organisation's optimal growth. This challenge is causing strain on both the organisation and its members.

This is of course typical in a young organisation, where people will work together to get things done that fall outside of anyone's official remit and that may not ordinarily be part of their role. However, with the success and high levels of demand that 2i2c already has, most people's bandwidth is already fully utilised in their primary role.

These additional responsibilities are resulting in fatigue and reduced productivity due to frequent context switching. This, in turn, affects the successful execution of tasks and initiatives, often leading to incomplete work and slower progress.

The fact that 2i2c is globally distributed and works primarily asynchronously is an extra challenge as initiatives and tasks that are outside of someone's primary remit often require additional collaboration across teams.

While process improvements are necessary to enhance efficiency (recommendations for which are provided later in this report), the primary challenge lies in the shortage of dedicated expertise and available bandwidth.

Key Recommendations

Our recommendations centre on identifying key activities that require more focus and expertise, along with defining the necessary roles to undertake these needs. At the same

time, we are mindful that adding new people is in itself a major change that requires careful management.

We have hence identified the minimal level of immediate hires that we believe are necessary to re-enable growth across the organisation. These are:

- One person to own crystallising the vision along with the planning and prioritisation to drive its implementation. They will also own the associated measurement, learning and continuous improvement processes.
- One person to organise, track, unblock and communicate progress both for the engineering team and for the organisation as a whole.
- One person to shape and manage the development of the organisation's culture and working environment. They will support the leaders of each function in looking after their people as well as organising the underlying organisational support processes.

In summary, these roles encompass a Product Manager, a combined Delivery Manager/ Chief of Staff, and a People Ops specialist, who will each play a vital role in enhancing 2i2c's organisational capabilities.

This executive summary offers a concise overview of the report's findings and recommendations. For a deeper understanding, please refer to the main body of the report

2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose

The purpose of this report is to assess the current state of your organisation, 2i2c. This assessment aims to identify key areas for improvement to support your growth and enhance your impact.

You have commissioned Difference Digital to help you determine the steps that you need to take now to address your current challenges whilst also setting the organisation up for ongoing and longer term success.

2.2. Background

2i2c is a young not-for-profit organisation who have had significant success in the course of the first two and half years of your existence. You enable educational and research organisations ('partners') to deploy open-source cloud based computing environments based on JupyterHub, without them needing any significant technical knowledge.

Your focus to date has been on ensuring excellence in the delivery of your product as well ensuring financial stability. You have excelled at this. Your partners are happy, your reputation is spreading by word of mouth, you recover 30-40% of your costs via fees and you've also raised large amounts of grant funding. This gives you a secure runway into 2025.

Your staff are of an extremely high calibre and have a strong alignment to 2i2c's mission, with many also having a long history of open source contribution to JupyterHub. Your combined extraordinary level of commitment and expertise has helped to build the success to date.

Your product has been extremely successful to the extent that you are now unable to take on more work without scaling your organisation. You want to ensure that you scale in a strategic fashion, working on improving processes and nurturing the people and culture whilst also designing the optimal structure and role profiles for your expanding team.

In our assessment, we have sought to be mindful of the unique nature and complexity of 2i2c and the need to harness and retain the significant qualities that you have.

You are unusual in a number of regards, with the key areas being:

- Your not-for-profit status and the strong alignment to your mission that your staff have, with many having volunteered for the same 'cause' for years in advance of joining.
- The way that the organisation straddles the Open Source world, with staff actively contributing to upstream JupyterHub issues that may not always be important for 2i2c.
- The global diversity of your team. This is magnified due to the small numbers (a total staff of eight people) meaning that there are very few working time overlaps with other team members.
- The exceptional calibre of your staff. You are typically hiring individuals who have already proven themselves as the most highly regarded engineers in an Open Source community and/or who have impressive academic backgrounds.
- The lack of previous experience of most staff in working in either more established technology organisations or startups, most people are on this kind of organisational growth journey for the first time.
- Due to the deep technical nature of your product and the experience and background of your engineers, your engineers have unique insights meaning that they can contribute to the product vision in a way that most engineering teams would not be able to do.
- Your product is not easily defined nor does it have firm boundaries, it has a tendency to evolve in response to requests from the wider open source community many of whom are not fee-paying partners.

2.3. Method

We employed the following methods in the process of the assessment:

Interviews - All members of staff, and one recent leaver, were interviewed to gain insights into their perspectives.

Observations - We had access to Github where all work and discussions are actively managed and recorded, and also to "Team Compass" a documentation platform which serves as a centralised hub for information and links to GitHub issues. Additionally, we were

included in various Slack channels which are used primarily for status updates and information sharing.

Consultations - We consulted a number of external parties who have experience of relevance, with a focus on asynchronous work practices and globally distributed teams.

3. Current State

3.1. Structure

Your organisation has just two functional areas, Engineering and Partnerships. Engineering develop and deliver your product. Partnerships acquire and manage the relationship with your partners, i.e. those educational and research establishments who pay for your services.

Engineering consists of four Engineers who report into a single Engineering Manager. One of those engineers is also the de-facto Technical Authority/Architect, having designed significant aspects of the product from the outset. He is also currently fulfilling the role of Tech Lead, with plans for rotation to other team members in the future.

Partnerships is headed up by a Partnerships Lead who in a commercial organisation would likely be described as a Head of Business Development. Reporting into him is a Community Lead who ensures the ongoing success of those Partnerships.

Your Executive Director, Chris Holdgraf, has overall responsibility for the organisation, with the Partnerships Lead and the Engineering Lead reporting directly to him.

Both Engineering and Partnerships are well run and delivering successfully and the organisational leadership is strong and effective. However, there are significant gaps due to the absence of other functional areas, specifically Product and Operations, and in the delivery of cross-functional and organisation-wide change and activities. This in turn puts strain on the team and on overall effectiveness.

3.2. Process

2i2c works asynchronously and you excel at this. The global distribution of your team has made it essential to run this way and has ensured that you develop and embed good practice in this regard. Most of your people have extensive experience within open source communities and so asynchronous working styles have carried naturally across into 2i2c. In addition you have researched and incorporated ideas from well known organisations who run asynchronously, for instance GitLab and Buffer.

You manage all discussions, issues and progress via GitHub, with things like reminders or more general updates being provided in Slack. This approach is used by all members of the team, not just the engineers, and is working well day-to-day. However, when it comes to cross-team initiatives and decisions where there is no single owner, the system is not making it easy to see, track and manage progress and ownership at the 'helicopter' level.

Decision making is largely collaborative and managed via discussion within a GitHub issue. There is however no way of easily seeing if a decision is overdue unless someone raises it for attention, e.g., via Slack. The tendency is towards slower decision taking due to a bias for achieving consensus and the inherent time delays in asynchronous communication. That said, there are also some occasions when decisions are taken too quickly without all impacted parties having had the opportunity to contribute.

You have spent a lot of time thinking about processes and this is embodied in your 'Team Compass' manual. The quality of this is notably higher than in other young organisations, with proper research having been done, group discussion having taken place, and with all submissions and updates being under version control via Github. This said, as there is no-one with the responsibility or bandwidth to own the implementation and iteration of these processes, they are not consistently followed and risk remaining solely as documentation.

You have ongoing issues with effective work management and prioritisation due to the reactionary nature of needing to respond to requests from the upstream JupyterHub open source community, which in turn contribute to your product. You have recently introduced a system of quarterly goals and planning along with an agile sprint approach to address this.

This planning and sprint process is relatively new and many team members have said that they are already seeing improvements. We would recommend continuing to practise and iterate on this. However, in our opinion you need two additional roles to make it successful, a product manager and a delivery manager. More detail is provided later in this report.

3.3. Culture & People

You have built a unique and attractive culture based on transparency, trust, openness and flexibility. Your team is incredibly committed both due to this culture and because of the alignment of their individual personal values with 2i2c's mission and vision. People enjoy working with 2i2c with a number saying that they could not imagine working anywhere else.

You have a relatively flat power structure however some informal power dynamics exist. A number of people have pre-existing relationships from being involved in the upstream JupyterHub community and three members of the team are also co-founders.

You are aware of these dynamics and are particularly concerned that new joiners to the organisation who don't have these pre-existing connections are fully welcomed and integrated. However, as yet, you do not have a formally defined or validated way of achieving this.

The combination of your values and mission means that you are able to attract a calibre of employees that would be the envy of most technology organisations. This drives an aspiration to build a working environment that excels in supporting and retaining them. You feel that you are currently falling short on this.

A majority of staff have mentioned concerns about signs of stress and burnout, especially in others. This is thought to be due to factors connected to open-source, reactive, asynchronous and remote working as well as overall team capacity and work management processes. A 'bias to yes' is an integral part of the culture and was cited by many individuals as a contributing factor.

4. Analysis

We have touched upon a number of issues above and will now provide more detail along with our recommendations to resolve them.

4.1. No single owner of, or deep experience in, Product

There is no single team or person who owns and looks after the Product. This results in it being a shared responsibility and hence no-one's top priority. As a team you lack experience specific to Product and the associated discipline and skill-sets.

The lack of clarity in the product vision is a concern for the team, as they struggle to identify and prioritise the features that would provide the most benefit.

Product is particularly complex for 2i2c as the direction and shape of the offering is by default determined by upstream requests from the wider JupyterHub community. The 'pull' nature of the work, coupled with the absence of a defined plan or measurement, makes it currently impossible to determine the time required for, and cost of, product delivery. You are not able to forecast the scaling needed to meet increased demand, or to set accurate pricing.

Comments from the team include:

"We don't have a product, we have people asking us for things and this helps set our product direction."

"We've made up the pricing, we don't know how much it costs us to service our partners"

"There is a bias to 'yes' that needs to be pushed back on"

"We need a dedicated, experienced product person"

Recommendation 1: Add a Product function

We suggest that you add a Product function at the earliest opportunity. For now, you should hire a single Product Lead, with a view to building out the function further in the future.

The Product function will be responsible for:

- Setting the vision for the Product, based on research and understanding of partner needs and the wider landscape.
- Defining the features that comprise the product.
- Planning of a roadmap to implement the product vision.
- Breakdown of the roadmap into implementation tasks.
- Prioritisation of product features and implementation tasks.
- Measuring and monitoring the speed, cost and success of delivery.
- Using such measurement to improve the flow of work as well as to inform pricing and scaling decisions.

It will be important that your Product Lead is someone who is experienced in garnering and distilling ideas from others, as opposed to someone intent on setting the vision as an individual. This is a very different role than in a commercial organisation where the Product Lead sets the direction and in effect tells the engineers what to build. That approach would of course be completely unsuitable for 2i2c as it is the engineers, along with Partnerships/Community, who have the knowledge that is needed to shape the product. Product's role will be to pull their knowledge and ideas together, thus crystallising the vision and forming a workable delivery plan.

You will be looking for someone who is naturally collaborative and takes a servant-leader approach. They will need to have a good level of technical understanding and be genuinely interested in the 2i2c offering, ideally having worked previously with platform teams and/or worked at a very detailed level alongside engineers. As measuring and improving efficiency is important for 2i2c to support scaling, it will be ideal if the successful candidate also has some experience in [Product Ops](#).

4.2. The Engineering Manager's focus and effectiveness are diluted by detailed day-to-day work management.

Your Engineering Manager, Damián, spends a significant amount of time planning, organising, and managing the day-to-day work of his team at a detailed level. This dilutes his focus and makes him less effective at the more strategic aspects of his role, both due to the associated reduction in available time, and the amount of context switching involved.

Your engineers are in effect the engine of your organisation, it is there that the most scaling will need to take place. The addition of engineers in a sustainable way is key to increasing your ability to deliver on your mission; to take on more partners and deliver more hubs.

Your engineering manager should be focussing on the strategic thinking and cross-organisational collaboration needed to increase the effectiveness of his team, supporting them in their roles and growth. He needs to design and foster the engineering processes, working practices, structure and culture that will enable you to grow to having multiple teams of exceptional engineers.

As you can see from the comments, the team appreciate the hands-on work that he does but in our opinion, this would be far better delegated:

"It's better now that Damián has started to hold people more accountable by ensuring that things get done. Previously lots of GitHub issues were left undone."

"Damian is great as supporting us by assigning clear reactive tasks"

"It's tricky for Damián to manage the board due to a lack of time"

"We are building up invisible technical debt by not having a clear lifecycle."

"Strategy seems to always be on the back burner"

Recommendation 2: Add a Delivery Manager

We suggest that you add a Delivery Manager who will be responsible for the detailed planning and day-to-day management of engineering tasks, and will also act as a servant-leader to resolve and remove any blockers that individual team members may be experiencing.

They will report into the Engineering Manager, taking direction from him and running the day-to-day on his behalf. They should be someone with experience in running agile delivery processes including planning, leading retrospectives, and driving continuous improvement.

4.3. Engineers feel overloaded and find it difficult to know what to prioritise

Your engineers without exception feel that there is too much work for them to do and in particular, they find it hard to know what to prioritise.

This is in part because of the lack of clarity around the product/vision and also because of the additional complexity brought about by their involvement in wider JupyterHub open source community work. They are balancing support, reactive and strategic tasks.

Reactive tasks frequently take priority for an individual over planned work. This is natural given the nature of the work and is not something that can or should be eliminated, but it should be managed and, where feasible, reduced. This can lead to unhealthy decisions to work outside of regular hours, increasing the risk of stress due to not completing the planned tasks that were deprioritised as a result.

You have already taken steps to address things with your new goal and sprint planning process and so good progress is being made in the right direction. It is however still far from resolved and further improvements are needed.

Note that in some cases this is made worse by someone having specialist knowledge or responsibilities in the sense that if an issue cannot be resolved by them, there is no-one else that can resolve it either in 2i2c or upstream. This creates an additional burden of responsibility for them.

Comments from the team included:

"It's natural to want to work on issues that you've raised yourself and it can be difficult to know if these are genuinely more important than other issues or tasks for 2i2c as a whole"

"Upstream work can interfere with completion"

"Previously everything was reactive, it wasn't clear what was most useful to do"

"It's useful to have specialisms, it doesn't make sense for everyone to be able to do everything, however it would be good to address single points of responsibility by looking to get one other person upskilled on a thing. This would reduce the burden of being the only person who can work on something."

Recommendation 3: Develop better prioritisation and measurement of engineering work

The Delivery Manager should work with others, in particular Product, to design a process for managing contentions with Sprint Goal work, support tasks, reactive tasks and individual's potentially non 2i2c upstream work.

The Product Manager should work with others, in particular the Delivery Manager and the Engineering Manager, to design a process to measure and track the flow of work through the team. Once this is in place they should implement a process of continuous review and improvement. This will then enable you to understand when and where to add additional engineering capacity in order to meet both current and future demand.

Recommendation 4: Identify and reduce single points of responsibility

We recommend that both now, and as you continue to scale, you look to reduce and remove single points of responsibility in particular for your engineers. This should be driven by your Engineering Manager. They should identify these single points of responsibility and task individuals with training up one other person in each of their areas of specialism. This could also mean including specialist skill-sets in hiring briefs for new team members.

The aim here is to ensure that all staff feel able to work within their standard hours, and to take adequate holidays, without worrying that jobs will be left undone or issues unresolved. Ideally this should extend to consideration of any specialisms with upstream work that is not 2i2c specific.

It will of course not always be possible to achieve this in a small organisation, however an explicit focus can and should improve things.

4.4. There is no-one with the bandwidth or responsibility to manage and facilitate cross-team work and processes

You have put considerable thought into how the organisation should operate. The result is your “Team Compass” repository where everything is documented and which links seamlessly through to GitHub. It is noteworthy that whenever we asked a question about how something works, you were able to point to a page in the Team Compass page that explained it. On the other hand, you invariably also then said that you weren’t confident that the particular process was being followed. With no one owning a process, it’s unlikely that it will be followed.

Furthermore, all work is formed as discussions/issues (in GitHub) but there is no roll-up into a project style plan or view. There is hence nowhere to easily see what actions are due when, and by which team member. This is particularly the case when a piece of work spans functions. A recent example is the planned move of ownership of Support from Engineering to Partnerships. There is a record of the discussion in GitHub but there isn’t anywhere where to easily see the associated steps and up-to-date progress.

With no one responsible for tracking and managing work that span functions, or for ensuring that the systems to do this exist and are fit for purpose, delivery can be slow, misunderstanding can arise, and things can be left undone.

This responsibility for this could be attributed to Chris, the Executive Director, as he is the only person whose remit spans across the whole organisation. However, it is far from an optimal use of his time to be in the detail of the implementation given his broader strategic responsibilities. He naturally does get involved in some instances but so doing diminishes his effectiveness in his broader role.

Comments from the team included:

“We need a system for getting things done, to manage delivery of things other than hubs/code.”

“Chris holds everything together but he has no support to implement things. We need him to delegate a lot more.”

“No one holds you accountable if you say something will get done and it doesn’t.”

“More visibility/transparency on work overall would be good. I want to be able to see and influence things that are important across the organisation.”

Recommendation 5: Add a Chief of Staff role

You need someone to be the steward of your cross-functional, organisation-wide processes and work; to assume day-to-day responsibilities for these. This will reduce the burden on your Executive Director enabling him to focus more fully on strategy, communication and growth.

We suggest that adding a junior to mid level Chief of Staff would be the right approach. This role could be filled by your Delivery Manager hire making it a combined role in the short term. With only four or five engineers to support, they should have some additional bandwidth once they are to speed with the day-to-day running. Additionally, this could enhance the role's appeal to an experienced candidate, as it offers opportunities for personal development. Ultimately, as your organisation grows larger, this will need to become a role in its own right.

Recommendation 6: Build a system to view and manage cross-functional work

Your Chief of Staff should design and implement a system for seeing and managing cross-functional work. This could for instance be based on your existing GitHub issues boards, or it could pull these into a more visual Kanban style view by integrating with a tool such as Trello or Mural. The important thing here is not the tool, it's the ownership of the process, along with its ongoing review and continuous improvement.

4.5. The process for decision making is unclear

Somewhat related to the above mentioned issue with cross-team work, there is no clear process for decision making.

The prevailing culture is to seek consensus from everybody, and this typically works very well. However, there is a frustration that this can be slow and that it may also discourage people from taking the initiative to experiment and innovate.

On the other hand, sometimes the discipline of waiting for everyone to contribute is skipped. This can happen when there is a pressure or desire to make a decision quickly. For instance, in order to respond to a valued partner in a timely manner. This becomes an issue, for instance, when someone who was not involved cannot fulfil a commitment made on their behalf

There is currently no simple way to track needed or made decisions, and no forums or process to handle outstanding decisions.

Comments from the team include:

“Sometimes people will just do things, they may decide quickly based on a discussion with one or two others, and then realise too late that others should have been part of the decision. Other times a decision is needed but doesn't happen or takes ages as we are trying to reach consensus”

“We need to figure out the forums”

“We are empowered to make decisions but in reality we always seek consensus”

“How does decision making work? There is no clear process”

“Who is responsible for decisions on specific topics?”

Recommendation 7: Build a system to view and manage decisions

Your Chief of Staff should design and implement a system for tracking and managing decisions . This could be a similar process as for cross-functional work above, with some additional thought given to determining who needs to be involved in different decisions, as well as if there need to be any associated forums.

Once again, it's the ownership of the system, along with its ongoing review and continuous improvement that is most important.

4.6. There are inherent challenges with asynchronous working

Whilst you excel at asynchronous working in terms of your process and discipline, there are of course some inherent challenges.

Overall, the asynchronous approach works well and people are happy with it. Many of the team mentioned that a recent reduction in synchronous meetings has been an improvement.

There does however appear to be a need for most people to feel and be more connected, and for a greater degree of informal interaction.

Comments from the team include:

"It would be good to be able to synchronously brainstorm with one other person first and then add things as an issue, this would speed things up."

"Async causes loneliness, isolation."

"Async is better than sync working which can be tiring."

"It's good that we avoid synchronous meetings - they would be difficult and not advisable because of timezones."

"Things are very asynchronous & this can mean that time is wasted - for instance if someone misunderstands what you are asking for and spends time working on something that you don't need, a quick conversation could avoid this."

"It's difficult to know if someone is open to you hopping on a quick call, there is the feeling of not wanting to interrupt someone. It would be good to be able to chat to others informally about whatever's on your mind."

Recommendation 8: Experiment with synchronous connections

We suggest that you experiment with ways of allowing for and encouraging less formal synchronous connections.

There are various options for approaching this. You could for instance ask each person to nominate one hour per week when they are available to chat. They would choose a time that is as accessible as possible for people in other timezones, and may also therefore change to accommodate different timezones on different weeks. Or, you could choose to

use tools such as [Donut](#); which automatically encourage people to schedule an informal virtual coffee with each other.

In the event that you want to try something in a group, then [Gatheround](#) can work well for informal breakout icebreaker style sessions including 1-1. Alternatively a virtual office environment such as [Gather Town](#) can work well, though the office may be a little empty until the team is larger.

Your offsite sessions will of course be another opportunity to explore this and foster deeper interpersonal relationships.

The important thing here is not the tools or approach but rather the discipline to treat this as a cultural Goal, in a similar way to the other quarterly goals. It's essential to outline specific tasks and designate someone responsible for collecting feedback and refining the approach.

4.7. There is widespread concern about stress and burnout

There is widespread concern about stress and burnout amongst team members. Multiple people mentioned having noticed signs of it, especially in others. This is not something that we explicitly asked about and hence it was both surprising and worrying that it came up so frequently. This is not typical in other young organisations of a similar size, except for often with the founders themselves, based on our experience.

On the other hand, it's worth noting that it is both healthy and helpful that people are openly discussing this, as that this is a good first step in starting to address the problem.

Several factors could be contributing to this issue, including:

- A lack of downtime with people keeping an eye on and responding to issues both for 2i2c and upstream within the wider open-source community, outside of working hours.
- A lack of downtime with people aiming to connect with others across time zones and hence in effect reducing their downtime even if breaks are taken in between.
- The isolation and loneliness that can be a factor of remote and asynchronous working.
- A lack of clear priorities with much of the work being reactive and hence having a reduced sense of achievement compared to delivering against set goals.
- A deep alignment of personal values to 2i2c's mission with an associated sense of shared responsibility leading to a tendency to overcommit.
- A sense of there simply being too much work to do.

Comments from the team include:

"Burn out is common in open source, people have to have your back"

"People are overloaded, we need to improve process and start to reduce stress, to have a better work/life balance"

"I'm worried that people are masking how burned out they are"

Recommendation 9: Focus on mechanisms to reduce stress

Many of our previous recommendations will help in addressing stress:

- Adding a Product Manager will help with people feeling that they are focussing on the right work, and on things that are adding value.
- Adding a Delivery Manager will help with the organisation and distribution of work, enabling people to focus on getting their primary tasks done.
- Measuring the flow of work will help with accurate capacity planning, which in turn will help with ensuring there are sufficient people for the amount of work.
- Reducing and removing single points of responsibility will enable people to hand off work to others, and be confident that they can take a break without having to worry that important issues won't be picked up.
- Adding a Chief of Staff role will lessen the strain of others picking up the management of cross-functional tasks and help with the wider organisation of work.
- Building systems for the management of cross-functional work and decisions will reduce the stress of not knowing where things are in terms of status, or what actions are expected of you.
- Fostering deeper one-to-one relationships will alleviate feelings of isolation and loneliness and enhance the team's informal support network.

In addition, we recommend that you explore structuring work and processes in such a way that enables team members to increase the length and quality of their downtime. Indeed, this is something that your Engineering Manager is already actively exploring.

It will be important, as each of these recommendations is followed, to consider if they are having the desired impact on stress; to measure, learn and iterate accordingly. We recommend that you consider setting a Goal related to this

Addressing stress and burnout will be a key focus for the People Ops hire suggested in our next and final recommendation overleaf. It should be noted that they may need to engage additional, specialist external help to assist them with this both in terms of effective measurement and effective resolution.

4.8. There is no-one with solid experience of people management or processes

Your organisation does not have anyone with significant experience of the management of people or the associated processes.

You have a unique combination of factors that require an extraordinary level of focus on people including:

- Widespread concern about stress and burnout.
- A need to continually stay ahead of the logistical, cultural and mental health challenges that can be a result of asynchronous, globally distributed working.
- The complexity that derives from working both for 2i2c and also contributing to the upstream open-source community.
- A lack of knowledge about, or process for, giving and receiving effective and supportive feedback and the associated fostering of continuous improvement.
- The need for effective onboarding processes in particular where someone does not have existing working relationships with team members from involvement in the upstream open source community.
- The need of managers across the organisation to have someone experienced to reach out to, for advice on people related matters both day-to-day and strategic.
- A bias towards hiring from academic and open-source communities, which by default does not bring experience of working within, or managing people in, a more formal and fast growth organisation.

Comments from the team include:

“As we evolve we need to be sure that staff at levels are getting the right guidance and support”

“There is no structured process to give and receive feedback, we don't know how to do it”

“Group discussions and decisions in a github repository are fine now as we are all friends but as we grow this won't work. If someone wants to take time off for a personal reason they won't necessarily be comfortable discussing it with everyone.”

“Burnout is a problem, do we have the experience in the team to know how to handle this?”

“No-one is responsible for people, pastoral care, team events”

Recommendation 10: Hire an exceptional People person

We recommend that you hire a specialist in People Ops. This individual should possess significant expertise in developing and supporting people as well as in designing and implementing the related operational systems and processes. Their responsibilities will include:

- Playing a pivotal role in implementing strategies and support mechanisms to promote well-being and reduce burnout risk.
- Leading efforts to navigate the challenges of asynchronous, globally distributed working, fostering a cohesive work environment and addressing mental health and work/life balance concerns.
- Leading on cultural Goals.
- Establishing structured processes for giving and receiving feedback and achieving professional growth; promoting a culture of continuous improvement.
- Designing and implementing effective onboarding and offboarding strategies.
- Acting as a trusted resource and advisor for people-related matters for your people managers.
- Designing and running the logistical side of people operations for instance running hiring processes, tracking that sufficient holiday is being taken, commissioning salary benchmarking or dealing with visa issues.
- Engaging external specialists when specialist advice is needed for specific issues or activities.

Ultimately, you will need an Operations function, headed by a Head of Operations or COO, responsible for all of the operational aspects of the organisation including people, finance, legal, logistics etc. We are however mindful of the need not to overload the organisation with new hires too quickly hence the suggestion to focus on People for the time being.

There is a possibility that you could attract a stronger candidate with the offer of a career path into COO, if that is something that interests them.

5. Conclusion

In the pages of this report, we have undertaken a comprehensive examination of 2i2c's current state, identifying strengths and uncovering areas in need of strategic refinement.

As an organisation you have achieved remarkable success in realising your mission. From your inception until now, you have built an environment that encourages excellence and thrives on the unique talents of your people. Users are delighted with your product, there is high demand from prospective new partners, and you are financially secure.

However, with success comes new challenges and opportunities. You are at an inflection point in your growth trajectory, there is a pressing need to evolve beyond the confines of immediate product delivery. The next phase of your journey demands a broader perspective - a holistic approach to organisational development that encompasses structure, processes, and culture.

Throughout this assessment, we have encountered enthusiastic, talented individuals who embrace their roles and responsibilities with dedication and commitment. Yet, we have also discerned strain and fatigue and a sense of there being a lack of progress on critical initiatives. Moreover, the global distribution of 2i2c and its asynchronous work model introduce additional complexities when addressing tasks that transcend team boundaries.

While improvements can be made to existing processes, the core challenge revolves around the need for specialised expertise and expanded capacity.

We have offered a set of key recommendations designed to propel 2i2c toward sustainable growth. These recommendations focus on vital activities that require heightened attention and expertise, with a particular emphasis on the additional roles that should be filled to ensure their successful implementation

We recommend immediate hiring of a Product Manager, a combined Delivery Manager/ Chief of Staff, and a People Ops specialist. Each will play a vital role in enhancing 2i2c's organisational capabilities.

In summary, the journey of 2i2c is one marked by achievement, innovation, and unwavering commitment to your mission. The challenges you face today are emblematic of a growing, dynamic organisation, and with an effective strategic direction, 2i2c is poised to continue its trajectory of success.

Appendix 1: Summary of Findings

Issues:

- A. There is no single owner of, or deep experience in, Product.
- B. The Engineering Manager's focus and effectiveness are diluted by detailed day-to-day work management.
- C. Engineers feel overloaded and find it difficult to know what to prioritise.
- D. There is no-one with the bandwidth or responsibility to manage and facilitate cross-team work and processes.
- E. The process for decision making is unclear.
- F. There are inherent challenges with asynchronous working.
- G. There is widespread concern about stress and burnout.
- H. There is no-one with solid experience of people management or processes.

Recommendations:

- 1. Add a Product function.
- 2. Add a Delivery Manager.
- 3. Develop better prioritisation and measurement of engineering work.
- 4. Identify and reduce single points of responsibility.
- 5. Add a Chief of Staff role.
- 6. Build a system to view and manage cross- functional work.
- 7. Build a system to view and manage decisions.
- 8. Experiment with synchronous connections.
- 9. Focus on mechanisms to reduce stress.
- 10. Hire an exceptional People person.

Appendix 2: Proposed plan of action from Chris

Here's a short proposed plan of action given the recommendations above:

 Proposed plan of action for hiring and organizational audit